

Terpenoid¹ and Coumarin Constituents of *Atalantia monophylla* Correa

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Isolation and characterisation of friedelin and epifriedelanol from the leaves and xanthyletin, marmesin and γ -sitosterol from the root-bark of *Atalantia monophylla* Correa are described. The leaves also furnished a sterol fraction in low yield, which appeared from mass spectrometry to be a mixture of γ -sitosterol, stigmasterol and campesterol or the corresponding isomers approximately in the ratio 7 : 3 : 2 respectively. Baeyer-Villiger oxidation of friedelin produced the corresponding seven-membered lactone derivative, named friedelalactone, the structure of which was confirmed by its mass spectrum. The mass fragmentation of xanthyletin, has also been discussed.

The various parts of *Atalantia monophylla* Corr. (Syn. *A. malabarica*) of the family Rutaceae are reported to exhibit medicinal properties². It was thus of interest to determine the chemical constituents of different parts of this plant. A report on the constituents of the oil from the leaves of this plant was published earlier³. Very recently, atalantin⁴, a new tetranortriterpenoid has been reported from its root-bark. We wish to record in the present communication the isolation of friedelin, epifriedelanol and a minute amount of sterol mixture from the leaves and xanthyletin, marmesin and γ -sitosterol from the root-bark of this plant. Characterisation of the constituents was achieved mainly on the basis of their physical and spectral (UV, IR, MS) analyses, preparation of suitable derivatives and in some cases by direct comparison (TLC, m.m.p and IR) with the corresponding authentic sample as recorded in the experimental part. Epifriedelanol [= friedelan-3- β -ol(axial)] isolated by us was found to be identical (m.m.p. IR, TLC) with sodium borohydride reduction product of friedelin. No alkaloidal constituent was found to be present in these parts of this plant.

Friedelin upon Baeyer-Villiger oxidation with perbenzoic acid furnished the corresponding seven-membered lactonic (IR : 1740 cm^{-1}) compound, friedelalactone (I), $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_2$ (M^+ 442), m.p. 230° [α]_D ± 0° (CHCl_3). In view of the recent report of a triterpene containing such a seven-membered lactonic moiety, named as apetalactone, from *Culophyllum apetalum*⁵ the natural occurrence of this seven-membered lactone derivative of friedelin is also expected.

1. Part VI in the Series 'Terpenoid and Related compounds'; Part V : S. K. Talapatra and Miss M. Bhattacharya, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 962; Part IV : see ref. 7.
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4. M. R. Thacker and O. K. Sabata, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 870
5. T. R. Govindachari, D. Prakash and N. Viswanathan, *Tetrahedron letters*, 1967, 4177; *J. Chem. Soc.*, (C), 1968, 1328.

The mass fragmentation behaviour of friedelactone has been found to be similar to that of friedelin⁶. As expected, an increase by 16 mass units was observed in the molecular ion peak (M^+442)(I) and the fragment ions *a* and *b* still retaining the lactonic moiety (ring A).

The sterol, m.p. 148-50° obtained in small amount from the leaves, though appeared to be γ -sitosterol from m.p. and homogeneous towards TLC, was revealed by mass spectrometry to be a mixture consisting of γ -sitosterol ($M^+ 414$), stigmasterol ($M^+ 412$) and campesterol ($M^+ 400$) (or the corresponding isomer or isomers) approximately in the ratio 7 : 3 : 2 respectively estimated from the relative abundance of the molecular ion peaks. This result again confirms our previous contention⁷ that the sterols isolated from different plants, and thought to be homogeneous from TLC behaviour may be a mixture of several similar compounds and this will be revealed by mass spectral studies. Only mass spectrometrically homogeneous sterol may be regarded as pure sterol.

The mass spectra⁸ of the two coumarins xanthyletin (II) and marmesin, isolated from the root-bark, have also been studied. The former exhibits only few peaks as reported⁹ recently. The loss of a —Me and CO (metastable peaks observed) gives rise to a stable aromatic system and hence further fragmentation is resisted. The mass fragmentation pattern exhibited by marmesin was found to be exactly the same as reported for this coumarin recently^{10,11}.

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EXPERIMENTAL

Chemical examination of the leaves of Atalantia monophylla : Isolation of friedelin—Dried and powdered leaves (320 g.) was soxhletted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) for 30 hrs. The crude concentrate, a dark gummy mass, showed three spots (R_f 0.7, 0.4 and 0.3) on silica gel microchromatoplate using benzene-chloroform (1 : 1) as developer. The extract showing the absence of alkaloidal constituents (negative Dragendorff test) was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina (90 g), elution being carried out with solvents of increasing polarity. Benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) (1 : 1) eluate fractions furnished a solid (R_f 0.7 in the same solvent system as above) crystallised from petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) in needles (30 mg), m.p. 254-55°, $C_{30}H_{50}O$ (M^+ 426), $[\alpha]_D -22^\circ$ (c 0.723 in $CHCl_3$); IR : 1710 cm^{-1} (six-membered ketone). It showed positive test for triterpene with Liebermann Burchardt reagent. The absence of unsaturation in the molecule was suggested by its negative colouration with tetranitromethane. These two observations in conjunction with the physical constants¹² of the compound suggested its identity with friedelin which was confirmed by a direct comparison (m.m.p., superimposable IR) with an authentic sample. In addition to molecular ion peak (M^+ 426, 100%) the significant peaks appeared at m/e (% base peak) 411(20), 341(10), 302(40), 273(60) and 205(60) in the mass spectrum⁶ of friedelin.

Isolation of epifriedelanol : The earlier benzene fraction of the above chromatogram furnished a homogeneous solid crystallising from chloroform in needles (15 mg), m.p. 276-78°, $[\alpha]_D +21^\circ$, (c 0.578 in $CHCl_3$), $C_{30}H_{52}O$ (M^+ 428), IR : 3500 cm^{-1} (OH). The compound gave positive test for triterpene with Liebermann Burchardt reagent and developed no yellow colour with tetranitromethane. The fragmentation pattern exhibited by this compound was similar to that of friedelin and thus in accord with its structure [m/e (% base peak) M^+ 428 (87.5), 413(55), 341 (3), 304 (12.5), 275 (100), 207 (37.5), 205(75), 189 (30) (m/e 207 $-H_2O$)]. The identity was finally established by direct comparison (m.m.p., TLC, IR) with the $NaBH_4$ reduction product [friedelan-3 β -ol (axial)] of friedelin.

Sodium borohydride reduction of friedelin : A solution of friedelin (50 mg) in dry tetrahydrofuran (1.5 ml) was treated with $NaBH_4$ (80 mg) and left for two days. The reaction mixture was poured into water and extracted with chloroform. Evaporation of the extract left a solid residue which crystallised from a chloroform-methanol mixture to give epifriedelanol (20 mg) in rods, m.p. 276-78°.

Baeyer-Villiger oxidation of friedelin : Friedelin (100 mg) was added to a solution of perbenzoic acid in chloroform (2% solution, 80 ml) containing catalytic amount of toluene-*p*-sulphonic acid. After being left at 0-5° for 72 hrs. the solution was washed with aqueous sodium carbonate and then with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated. The resulting residue (60 mg) was dissolved in minimum quantity of petroleum ether and chromatographed over Brockmann alumina. The early benzene eluate fractions yielded unreacted crude friedelin (40 mg). The middle benzene fractions showing a different more polar spot were combined which upon concentration yielded friedelalactone (8 mg), as white crystalline solid m.p. 230°, (R_f 0.65 silica gel microchromatoplate, $CHCl_3$ developer.)

12. P. R. Jefferies, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 473.

(M^+ 442), $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$ (CHCl_3): IR : 1740 cm^{-1} (7-membered lactone); besides M^+ (72.5%) the following peaks appeared in its mass spectrum : m/e (% base peak) 318 (40), 289 (27.5), 273 (50), 205 (100), 189 (40), 177 (60), 149 (55) and 137 (80).

Isolation of sterols : The later benzene eluates and the earlier benzene-ether (1 : 1) eluates of the chromatogram of the original petroleum ether extract gave another solid crystallising from chloroform-methanol mixture in needles (10 mg), m.p. $146-49^\circ$. This upon rechromatography over small amount of alumina and crystallisation from chloroform-methanol mixture afforded crystals (5 mg) melting at $148-50^\circ$. The latter which responds to Liebermann Burchardt reaction for sterols, appeared to be homogeneous towards TLC (showing single spot in different solvent systems) but was found to be a mixture of sterols only when examined mass spectrometrically (vide *supra*). Further attempts to isolate the sterols in the pure state from their mixture could not be made for the time being because of the paucity of the material.

Chloroform extract of the leaves of A. monophylla : This extract (like petroleum ether extract showed negative test for alkaloid with Dragendorff's reagent) did not show any well-defined spot on the microchromatoplate when developed with different solvent system. In fact, the gummy residue (1.5 g) of the chloroform extract upon usual chromatography over neutral alumina did not afford any crystalline or amorphous solid from the gummy residue of different eluate fractions.

Alcoholic extract of this plant material : Upon similar processing the extract did not afford any pure compound whatsoever.

Chemical investigation of the root-bark of A. monophylla : Dried and powdered root-bark (1.8 Kg) of *A. monophylla* was Soxhletted with petroleum ether (b.p. $60-80^\circ$) and then with chloroform. The petroleum ether extract concentrate (showing three distinct spots in TLC) was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina, elution being carried out with solvents of increasing polarity.

Isolation of xanthyletin : The petroleum ether eluates showing a single spot in TLC yielded upon concentration a pale yellow crystalline solid, m.p. $114-19^\circ$. This was recrystallised twice from petroleum ether (b.p. $40-60^\circ$) in large colourless prisms when the melting point rose to 130° . The compound showed positive test for coumarin with ethanolic KOH, UV : λ_{max} (EtOH) $224\text{m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.20), 265 (4.26) and 344 (4.09); IR : γ_{max} (nujol) 1710 cm^{-1} (6-membered conjugated lactone), 1620 and $1550(-\text{C}=\text{C}-)$. Petroleum ether-benzene (95 : 5) eluates furnished a further quantity (60 mg) of the above coumarin in pure state, m.p. 130° (total yield, 150 mg). The above physical and spectral data suggested the identity of the coumarin with xanthyletin and this was established by direct comparison with an authentic sample of xanthyletin (m.m.p., superimposable IR).

Isolation of γ -sitosterol : The petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) fractions gave needle-shaped crystals (20 mg) of γ -sitosterol, m.p. $147-48^\circ$, $[\alpha]_D -41^\circ$ (c, 0.620 in CHCl_3), its identity was confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample¹ and by preparing its acetate, m.p. 142° , $[\alpha]_D -38^\circ$ (c, 0.572 in CHCl_3) in the usual way.

Isolation of marmesin : The benzene eluate fractions yielded another coumarin (ethanolic-KOH test) crystallising from petroleum ether-chloroform in needles, m.p. 187°, $[\alpha]_D^{+26}$ (*c* 0.721 in CHCl_3); λ max (EtOH) 226 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.13) and 337 (4.34); γ_{max} 3450 cm^{-1} (OH), 1710 (6-membered lactone), 1630 and 1570 ($-\text{C} = \text{C}-$). The identity of this coumarin with marmesin as suggested by above data, was finally confirmed by direct comparison (m.m.p. and IR) with an authentic sample isolated from the stem-bark of *Evodia fraxinifolia* Hook. f. in this laboratory¹³. Its mass fragmentation pattern [m/e (% base peak) M^+ 246 (50), 213 (21), 188(83), 187 (100), 160 (29), 131(17) and 59(85)] was found to be identical with that appeared in the literature^{10,11} recently.

The authors wish to express their sincere thanks to Dr. B. C. Das for mass spectral measurements⁸, to Dr. S. C. Pakrashi and to Dr. R. S. Kapil for IR spectra, to Dr. A. K. Das Gupta and to Dr. A. K. Bhattacharya for authentic samples of xanthyletin and friedelin respectively and to Dr. T. K. Bose for the gift of the plant materials. Financial assistance from USEFI by way of an Alumni Research Grant (SKT) is gratefully acknowledged.

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Received September 25, 1969

13. S. K. Talapatra and B. Talapatra, unpublished work.